

Controlling gene expression and viral diseases by using music waves

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In this research, we show that motions of DNAs within the cells produce a natural music waves. This special music wave produce some hexagonal and pentagonal holes within the cells. These holes can be filled by viral RNA and DNA bases which their energies are equal to negative energies of holes. To control these viruses, we can use of some music waves that produce extra energies within cells and remove these holes. We argue that frequency of initial music wave changes by passing gates on the cell and nuclear membranes. After passing music waves from nuclear barriers, natural music wave of DNA changes and some extra signals are emerged which are transformed to the heart by neurons. Heart acts like a CPU, analyse them and send some messages to the brain as the body's memory and monitor. Brain divides these signals into two parts, transforms one part to eyes and another to skin cells as the biological antenna. We detect radiated waves of eyes and skin cells for two groups, one who had Influenza and another without any virus. We show that music waves can control viral diseases.

Keywords: Gene Expression, Music waves, Brain, heart, DNA

I. INTRODUCTION

Up to date, many investigations on music therapy and music medicine have been done and various methods have been proposed. For example, in one research, authors have compared the impact of music therapy (MT) versus music medicine (MM) interventions on psychological outcomes and pain in cancer patients and to enhance understanding of

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patients' experiences of these two types of music interventions [1]. In another investigation, authors have indicated that music interventions may have beneficial effects on anxiety, pain, fatigue and QoL in people with cancer. Furthermore, music may have a small effect on heart rate, respiratory rate and blood pressure [2]. In another paper, investigators have shown that music therapy and progressive muscle relaxation training can reduce depression, anxiety and length of hospital stay in female breast cancer patients after radical mastectomy [3]. In another work, researchers have found that Music-based interventions have positive effects on cancer patients' anxiety, depression, pain, life quality of life. They have shown that greater reductions of anxiety and depression can be observed in breast cancer [4]. Another research has explored the effects of music therapy on self-reported symptoms of patients receiving inpatient care at a comprehensive cancer center. It has been shown that a single, in-person, tailored music therapy intervention as part of an integrative oncology inpatient consultation service contributed to the significant improvement in global, physical, and psychosocial distress [5]. Other researchers have shown that individual music therapy sessions may be effective to reduce fatigue related to cancer and symptoms of depression, as well as to improve quality of life for women with breast or gynecological cancer undergoing radiotherapy [6]. Also, another investigators have considered effects of music therapy on mood and pain with patients hospitalized for bone marrow transplantation. They have shown that although no result was significant, there were positive changes resultant of patient-preferred live music in pain, relaxed/anxious, wide awake/drowsy, and cheerful/depressed in the experimental group [7]. And in one of newest works, authors have demonstrated music as a modulator of gene expression in a cancer cell line [8]. Now, the question arises that how music waves could control viral diseases? We answer this question by considering the behaviour of DNAs within the cells. We show that motion of DNAs within cells produce some music waves. These waves create some hexagonal and pentagonal holes. These holes could attract viral DNA and RNA bases. To prevent of viral diseases, we use of some music waves. These waves pass the cell and nuclear barriers and become stronger. These waves fill holes and repel viral DNAs and RNAs. We test the model with experiments.

The outline of the paper is as follows. In section II, we propose a model for controlling gene expression and viral diseases by music waves. In section III, we test the model with experiments. The last section is devoted to conclusions.

II. A MODEL FOR CONTROLLING GENE EXPRESSION AND VIRAL DISEASES BY MUSIC WAVES

In this section, we propose a mathematical model to calculate number of micro-states of a DNA. We show that by rotation of DNA, a negative current is emerged and some hexagonal and pentagonal holes are emerged. This current evolves with time and produce a natural music wave. These holes can be filled by viral RNA and DNA viruses (See figure 1). We can write:

$$\Omega_{DNA-holes} \times \Omega_{viralRNA/DNA} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega_{DNA-holes}$ is the number of microstates of DNAs and $\Omega_{viralRNA/DNA}$ is the number of microstates of viral RNA/DNAs. To prevent of viral diseases, we should produce some music waves that pass the cell gates and produce some structures for filling these holes (See Figure 2). We can write:

$$\Omega_{DNA-holes} \times \Omega_{musicwaves} = 1 \quad (2)$$

where $\Omega_{musicwaves}$ is the number of microstates which are emerged by music waves. These music waves cause to motion of charged particles and produce by motion of charges, according to laws of physics, some transverse electromagnetic and longitudinal music waves are emerged. Also, density of matters within the cells is more respect to around it and velocity of matters and frequency of music waves increase. These waves again pass second barrier related to nuclear membrane, become again stronger and produce shorter transverse electromagnetic and longitudinal music waves. We can write:

$$\omega_{music-out-cell} < \omega_{music-within-cell} < \omega_{music-within-nucleus} \quad (3)$$

where $\omega_{music-out-cell}$ is the frequency out of cell, $\omega_{music-within-cell}$ is the frequency within the cell, $\omega_{music-within-nucleus}$ is the velocity within the nucleus.

These stronger waves, increase the velocity of rotation of DNAs, produce some extra hexagonal and pentagonal structures and fill holes.

FIG. 1: Rotation of a DNA produce some hexagonal and pentagonal holes which could be filled by viral RNA bases.

Now, we should consider properties of space-time which DNA communicate with each other inside it. These properties help us to obtain wave equations. To explain these properties, we should introduce a metric. This metric explains the relation between times and spaces. For example, in normal conditions, time and space are orthogonal to each other in a four dimensional page. This medium is called Minkowski space-time. However, for an observer in nano scale, DNA is an object with 7 meter long which contracts in small place. This produces a curved space-time around a DNA (See figure 1). Consequently, in this medium, normal time and space are mixing with each other and produce a new metric. Without metric, we couldnt consider evolutions of waves which are exchanged between DNA. To consider the Bionic DNA, we specialize to an embedding of the DNA world volume in Minkowski space-time with metric [9–14];

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + dr^2 + r^2(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2) + \sum_{i=1}^6 dx_i^2 \quad (4)$$

without background fluxes. Here, t is time, r is the radius of page of DNA and θ is the angle of rotation. The action of this Bionic DNA can be given by:

$$S = -T_{tri} \int d^3\sigma \sqrt{\eta^{ab} g_{MN} \partial_a \phi^M \partial_b \phi^N + 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}$$

$$G = \left(\sum_{n=1}^N \frac{1}{n!} \left(-\frac{F_1 \dots F_n}{\beta^2} \right) \right)$$

$$F = F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \quad F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \quad (5)$$

where g_{MN} is the background metric, $\phi^M(\sigma^a)$'s are scalar fields which are produced by pairing electrons ($\phi = \psi_{up}\psi_{down}$), N is number of exchanged photons between DNAs, σ^a 's are the DNA coordinates, $a, b = 0, 1, \dots, 3$ are world-volume indices of DNA and $M, N = 0, 1, \dots$, are number of paired electrons. Also, G is the nonlinear field [9] and A is the photon which exchanges between DNAs.

Using the metric in equation (4), we can write below relations between coordinates of bulk and Bionic DNA [9]:

$$t(\sigma) = \tau \quad r(\sigma) = \sigma, \quad x_1(\sigma) = z \quad (6)$$

Using above relations, for this Bionic DNA in flat space time, the action is given by [?]:

$$S = - \int d\sigma \sigma^2 \sqrt{1 + z'^2 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)} \quad (7)$$

For this action, it has been asserted that momentum density is given by [9]:

$$\Pi = \frac{2\pi l_s^2 G'(F) F_{01}}{\sqrt{1 + z'^2 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}} \quad (8)$$

where $'$ denotes the derivative respect to the field (F). On the other hand, it has been asserted that there is a relation between momentum density and σ [9]:

$$\Pi = \frac{K}{\sigma^2} \quad (9)$$

Using equations (8 and 9) and assuming ($z' \ll G(F)$), we can obtain :

$$\sigma = \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}}{2\pi l_s^2 G'(F) F_{01}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (10)$$

Above equation shows that coordinates of Bionic DNA depend on non-linear fields and increase by increasing the strength of fields. We also obtain the acceleration, with taking derivative of above coordinate respect to time:

$$a = \frac{d^2\sigma}{dt^2} = \left[\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}}{2\pi l_s^2 G'(F) F_{01}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \quad (11)$$

Above equation shows that nonlinear electromagnetic waves lead to the acceleration of system. This acceleration changes physical properties of system. In this case, the relation between the world volume coordinates of the DNA (τ, σ) and the coordinates of Minkowski space-time (t, r) are [9];

$$at = e^{a\sigma} \sinh(a\tau) \quad ar = e^{a\sigma} \cosh(a\tau) \quad (12)$$

where a is the acceleration of rotating DNA. We can suppose that the coordinate along the separation distance between Dndrite and DNA's terminals ($x^4 = z$) depends on the $r = \pm \frac{1}{a} e^{\pm a\sigma} \cosh(a\tau)$ and by using equations (12), rewrite equations (4) as [9];

$$\begin{aligned} ds_I^2 = & -dt^2 + \left(1 + \left(\frac{dz}{dr}\right)^2\right) dr^2 + r^2 \left(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2\right) + \sum_{i=1}^5 dx_i^2 = \\ & \left(e^{2a\sigma} + \frac{1}{\sinh^2(a\tau)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau}\right)^2\right) d\tau^2 - \left(e^{2a\sigma} + \frac{1}{\cosh^2(a\tau)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\sigma}\right)^2\right) d\sigma^2 + \\ & \frac{1}{\sinh(a\tau) \cosh(a\tau)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \frac{dz}{d\sigma}\right) d\tau d\sigma + \left(\frac{1}{a} e^{a\sigma} \cosh(a\tau)\right)^2 \left(d\theta^2 + \sin^2\theta d\phi^2\right) + \sum_{i=1}^5 dx_i^2 \quad (13) \end{aligned}$$

Now, we can replace acceleration with it's equivalent temperature. To obtain true relation between temperature and acceleration, we use of concepts of BIon:

$$dM_{I-A/B} = T_{I-A/B} dS_{I-A/B} \rightarrow T_{I-A/B} = \frac{dM_{I-A/B}}{dS_{I-A/B}} \quad (14)$$

Previously, thermodynamical parameters have been obtained in [9]:

$$\begin{aligned} dM_{I-A} &= \frac{dM_{I-A}}{dz_{I-A}} dz_{I-A} \\ dz_{I-A} &= dz_{II-B} \simeq \left(e^{-4a\sigma} \sinh^2(a\tau) \cosh^2(a\tau) \right) \times \\ & \left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma) \left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma)}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma_0)} - e^{-4a(\sigma - \sigma_0)} \frac{\cosh^2(a\tau_0)}{\cosh^2(a\tau)} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma) \left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma)}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma_0)} - e^{-4a(\sigma - \sigma_0)} \frac{\cosh^2(a\tau_0)}{\cosh^2(a\tau)} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\sinh^2(a\tau_0)}{\sinh^2(a\tau)} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{dM_{I-A}}{dz} &= \frac{dM_{II-B}}{dz} = \frac{4T_{D3}^2}{\pi T_{0,I-A}^4} \frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\sigma, \tau) \left(\frac{1}{a} e^{a\sigma} \cosh(a\tau)\right)^2 \left(\sinh^2(a\tau) + \cosh^2(a\tau)\right)}{\sqrt{F_{DBI,I,A}^2(\sigma, \tau) - F_{DBI,I,A}^2(\sigma_0, \tau)}} \times \\
&\frac{4 \cosh^2 \alpha_{I-A} + 1}{\cosh^4 \alpha_{I-A}} \\
dS_{I-A} &= dS_{II-B} = \frac{4T_{D3}^2}{\pi T_{0,I-A}^5} \frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\sigma, \tau) \left(\frac{1}{a} e^{a\sigma} \cosh(a\tau)\right)^2 \left(\sinh^2(a\tau) + \cosh^2(a\tau)\right)}{\sqrt{F_{DBI,I,A}^2(\sigma, \tau) - F_{DBI,I,A}^2(\sigma_0, \tau)}} \times \\
&\frac{4}{\cosh^4 \alpha_{I-A}}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

using relation (15) in relation (14), we can obtain explicit form of temperature in an accelerating DNA:

$$\begin{aligned}
T_{I-A} &= T_{0,I-A} \left(4 \cosh^2 \alpha_{I-A} + 1\right) \times \\
&\left(e^{-4a\sigma} \sinh^2(a\tau) \cosh^2(a\tau)\right) \times \\
&\left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma) \left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma)}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau, \sigma_0)} - e^{-4a(\sigma-\sigma_0)} \frac{\cosh^2(a\tau_0)}{\cosh^2(a\tau)}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma) \left(\frac{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma)}{F_{DBI,I,A}(\tau_0, \sigma_0)} - e^{-4a(\sigma-\sigma_0)} \frac{\cosh^2(a\tau_0)}{\cosh^2(a\tau)}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}}} - \frac{\sinh^2(a\tau_0)}{\sinh^2(a\tau)}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}
\end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Above equations show the explicit relation between temperatures and acceleration in a DNA. However to obtain the relation between temperature and rotating velocity, we should take a derivation of above equations, put ($\omega = \frac{d\sigma}{dt}$) and obtain below relation:

$$a = \left[\frac{d^2}{dt^2} \left[\frac{\sqrt{1 - 2\pi l_s^2 G(F)}}{2\pi l_s^2 G'(F) F_{01}}\right]^{\frac{1}{2}}\right] \sim \frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]}{\left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tag{17}$$

where T_0 is temperature of non-rotating DNA and ω is the frequency. Also, ω_0 is the upper limit frequency of DNA. Substituting equation (17) in equations (13), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
ds_I^2 &= \\
&2 \frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]}{\left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma \\
&\left(e^{\frac{1}{\sinh^2\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} \left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]}{\left[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}\right]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau\right)}} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau}\right)^2\right) d\tau^2 -
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left(e^{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma} + \frac{1}{\cosh^2 \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\sigma} \right)^2 \right) d\sigma^2 + \\
& \frac{1}{\sinh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) \cosh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \frac{dz}{d\sigma} \right) d\tau d\sigma + \\
& \left(\frac{1}{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} e^{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma} \cosh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) \right)^2 \times \\
& \left(d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\phi^2 \right) + \\
& \sum_{i=1}^5 dx_i^2
\end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Above metrics are corresponded to thermal rotating DNA. These metric depends on the temperature and rotating velocity of DNA. To obtain the spectrum of rotating DNA, we should obtain the action. With the metric of equation (18), the action (5) should be re-written as:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{I,end1} = & - \int dt \int_{\sigma_0}^{\infty} d\sigma \left(-e^{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma} \cosh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) \right)^2 \times \\
& \left(\sinh^2 \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) + \cosh^2 \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) \right) \times \\
& \left[1 + \frac{e^{-2 \frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma}}{\sinh^2 \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \right)^2 + \frac{e^{-2 \frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma}}{\cosh^2 \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\sigma} \right)^2 + \right. \\
& \left. \frac{e^{-2 \frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sigma}}{\sinh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right) \cosh \left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1} [1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1 - \frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}} \tau \right)} \left(\left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \frac{dz}{d\sigma} \right) - (2\pi l_s^2 G(F)) \right)^2 \right]^{1/2}
\end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Using the method in ref [14], we can obtain the area from equation (19) for each molecule of DNA:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{N-gonal} &\sim A_{N-gonal} = \int d^3\sigma \varrho_{I,end1} \\
\varrho_{I,end1} &= \left[1 + \frac{e^{-2\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}}}{\sinh^2\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau}\right)^2 + \frac{e^{-2\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}}}{\cosh^2\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\sigma}\right)^2 + \right. \\
&\quad \left. \frac{e^{-2\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}}}{\sinh\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right) \cosh\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right)} \left(\frac{dz}{d\tau} \frac{dz}{d\sigma}\right) \right]^{1/2} O_{tot,N} \\
O_{tot,N} &= \left[1 + \frac{k_3^2}{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} \right]^{-1/2} \times \dots O_{tot,1} \\
O_{tot,N-1} &\left(\frac{1}{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} e^{-\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} \cosh\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right) \right)^4 \\
O_{tot,1} &= \left[1 + \frac{k_2^2}{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} \right]^{-1/2} \\
&\left(\frac{1}{\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} e^{-\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\sigma}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}} \cosh\left(\frac{T_0 \ln^{-1}[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]\tau}{[1-\frac{\omega^2}{\omega_0^2}]^{\frac{1}{4}}}\right) \right)^4
\end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

where N is the number of sides or corners of hexagonal or pentagonal manifolds in each DNA. To calculate total area of a DNA, we should sum over areas of hexagonal and pentagonal manifolds.

$$A_{DNA} = \sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^M A_{n,i} \tag{21}$$

This area depends on temperature and the angular velocity of rotating DNA. In a biological system like a cell, DNA is compacted four times around various axes and temperature is very large. This causes that total area of DNA grows and achieve to large values.

Each rotating DNA radiates a wave which it's frequency is equal to rotating velocity of DNA. If this wave achieves to a metal, leads to the motion of it's electrons and production of a current. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
E_{radiation,DNA} &= \hbar\omega_{DNA} = \hbar\omega_{0,DNA} + \rho I_{Current,DNA}^2 \implies \\
\omega_{DNA} &= [\omega_{0,DNA} + \frac{\rho I_{Current,DNA}^2}{\hbar}]
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

By replacing above relation in equation (21), we can obtain area of a DNA in terms of current. Above equation shows that area of a DNA has a relation with current which is produced by its wave in a metal. This helps us to measure area of a DNA by evolutions of currents in a lab. Also, Tsallis and Cirto have argued that the entropy of a gravitational system such as a black brane could be extended to the non-additive entropy, which is given by $S = \gamma A^\beta$, where A is the horizon area [13]. We can write:

$$\bar{S}_I = \gamma A_{DNA}^\beta \tag{23}$$

Above equation shows that entropy of a DNA has a relation with current which is produced by its wave in a metal. This helps us to measure entropy of a DNA by evolutions of currents in a lab. On the other hand, entropy has a relation with number of microstates of a DNA:

$$\bar{S}_I = K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \tag{24}$$

Using equations (20, 23 and 24), we obtain number of microstates of a DNA in terms of current:

$$\Omega_{DNA} = \frac{1}{K_B} e^{\gamma A_{DNA}^\beta} = \frac{1}{K_B} e^{\gamma [\sum_{n=1}^N \sum_{i=1}^M A_{n,i}]^\beta} \tag{25}$$

This number helps us to obtain the exact number of microstates of a DNA in terms of currents in a lab. When a DNA rotates, it radiates a wave. This wave leads to motion of electrons in a wire and a current is emerged. This current gives exact information about evolution of a DNA.

Rotation of a DNA could lead to the emergence of some hexagonal and pentagonal holes. These holes have negative energy and produce a negative force. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{DNA} \times \Omega_{DNA-hole} &= 1 \\
\rightarrow \bar{S}_{DNA-hole} &= K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA-hole}) = -K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow E_{DNA-hole} &= K_B T \log(\Omega_{DNA-hole}) = -K_B T \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow F_{DNA-hole} &= \frac{\partial E_{DNA-hole}}{\partial \sigma} < 0
\end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

where $F_{DNA-hole}$ is the force which is emerged by DNA-holes, $E_{DNA-hole}$ is the energy which is emerged by DNA-holes, $\bar{S}_{DNA-hole}$ is the entropy which is emerged by DNA-holes and T is temperature. Above equation shows that rotation of a DNA produces some extra microstates corresponded to some hexagonal and pentagonal holes. These holes produce a nequative energy and force which makes the system un-stable. To produce an stable conditions, some viral RNA and DNA structures could fill these holes. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{viral-DNA/RNA} \times \Omega_{DNA-hole} &= 1 \\
\rightarrow \bar{S}_{viral-DNA/RNA} &= K_B \log(\Omega_{viral-DNA/RNA}) = K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow E_{viral-DNA/RNA} &= K_B T \log(\Omega_{viral-DNA/RNA}) = K_B T \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow F_{viral-DNA/RNA} &= \frac{\partial E_{viral-DNA/RNA}}{\partial \sigma} > 0 \\
\rightarrow F_{viral-DNA/RNA} + F_{DNA-hole} &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

where $F_{viral-DNA/RNA}$ is the force which is emerged by viral DNA/RNA, $E_{viral-DNA/RNA}$ is the energy which is emerged by viral DNA/RNA, $\bar{S}_{viral-DNA/RNA}$ is the entropy which is emerged by viral DNA/RNA and T is temperature. To avoid of these viral diseases, we can use of music waves. These waves pass cell and nuclear membranes, become more stronger, produce hexagonal and pentagonal structures and fill holes. We can write:

$$\begin{aligned}
\Omega_{Music-hole} \times \Omega_{DNA-hole} &= 1 \\
\rightarrow \bar{S}_{Music-hole} &= K_B \log(\Omega_{Music-hole}) = K_B \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow E_{Music-hole} &= K_B T \log(\Omega_{Music-hole}) = K_B T \log(\Omega_{DNA}) \\
\rightarrow F_{Music-hole} &= \frac{\partial E_{Music-hole}}{\partial \sigma} > 0 \\
\rightarrow F_{Music-hole} + F_{DNA-hole} &= 0
\end{aligned} \tag{28}$$

where $F_{Music-holeA}$ is the force which is emerged by music-holes, $E_{Music-hole}$ is the energy which is emerged by music-holes, $\bar{S}_{Music-hole}$ is the entropy which is emerged by music-holes and T is temperature. Thus, music waves could prevent of viral diseases by producing some hexagonal and pentagonal structures and filling DNA-holes.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

When music waves pass the cell and nuclear membranes, change DNA music waves and produce new hexagonal and pentagonal structures. These waves are transformed into the heart by neurons. Heart acts like a CPU, analyse extra waves and send results to the brain. Brain acts like a memory and save these informations. Also, it acts like a monitor and display these changes by using eye and skin antennas. We can use of a metal or graphene sheet to take radiated signals of eyes and skin cells during playing music (See figure 3). In figure 4, we present radiated signals which are taken from a healthy person during playing a normal music. We observe that by passing time, intensity of emitted waves increase. This is because that music waves pass the nuclear membrane and change DNA music waves. These waves are transformed to the heart, brain and eyes (See figure 4). In figure 5, we show radiated signals from eyes in a non-healthy body (suffering Influenza) during playing music. It is observed that by passing time, emitted waves decrease. This is because that viral RNAs which are attracted by DNA-holes within the cells, repel by music waves. Consequently, DNA waves return to normal conditions and cells become stable. In figure 6, we present currents in a metal/graphene sheet on the skin near the heart (blue) and the skin near the nervous system (red) for a healthy body during playing music. It is clear that near the heart, skin cells emit more signals, because the heart is the CPU of system and send analysed data to antenna and brain. Also, both currents increase and tend to a constant values. Because music waves increase frequency of DNA waves and consequently, more signals are radiated by antenna. In figure 7, we present currents in a metal/graphene sheet near the eye for a healthy body during playing music. These currents increase and tend to a constant values. Because music waves increase frequency of DNA waves and consequently, more signals are radiated by eyes. In figure 8, we present currents in a metal/graphene sheet near the eye (blue color) and skin (red color) for anon-healthy body (suffering Influenza) during playing music. These currents decrease and tend to a constant values. Because music waves repel

viral RNA/DNAs which are filled DNA holes within the cells. Consequently, the stress and intensity of diseases decreases and less signals are emitted by eye and skin antenna.

FIG. 3: any change in DNA music wave can be transformed through neurons to the heart (CPU of human's body) by a subsequent to the brain and then to eye and skin antennas.

FIG. 4: Radiated signals of eyes in a healthy body are taken by Radio-Skypipe during playing music

FIG. 5: Radiated signals of eyes in a non-healthy body (suffering Influenza) are taken by Radio-Skypipe during playing music

FIG. 6: Currents in terms of time for radiated signals of skin near heart (red color) and skin near central nervous system (blue color) in a healthy body are taken by Radio-Skype during playing music

IV. SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

In this paper, we have argued that the vibration of a DNA within the cell creates a special music wave. This vibration and its related music wave lead to the emergence of some hexagonal and pentagonal holes. These holes are a unique opportunity for viruses that their RNA and DNA bases fill them. To avoid entering viruses into cells, we should use some music waves that their energies be equal to energies of holes. We have shown that music waves change by passing cell and nuclear membrane and become more stronger. These waves produce extra structures which fill holes and change music waves of DNAs. Neurons transform changes in music waves to the heart and then, heart analyzes them like a CPU. This biological CPU sends some information to brain. Brain acts like the monitor and sends waves to eye and skin antenna. We detect effects of music waves on cells by considering

FIG. 7: Currents in terms of time for radiated signals of eyes in a healthy body are taken by Radio-Skypipe during playing music

radiated signals from skin cells and eyes. We show that these signals are different for persons with viral diseases and healthy ones.

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FIG. 8: Currents in terms of time for radiated signals of eyes (blue color) and skin (red color) in a non-healthy body (suffering Influenza) are taken by Radio-Skypipe during playing music

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